

Machine learning-based real-time power stability optimization for photovoltaic systems using hybrid inductor-capacitor patterns

Jayashree Kathirvel¹, S. Pushpa², P. Kavitha³, Sathya Sureshkumar⁴, Kannan Andi⁵,
Prabakaran Pramasivam⁶

¹Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Rajalakshmi Engineering College, Chennai, India

²Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Panimalar Engineering College, Chennai, India

³Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, R.M.K. Engineering College, Chennai, India

⁴Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, S.A. Engineering College, Chennai, India

⁵Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institute (Deemed to be University), Chennai, India

⁶Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Chennai Institute of Technology, Chennai, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 19, 2024

Revised Nov 13, 2025

Accepted Nov 28, 2025

Keywords:

Hybrid inductor-capacitor networks

Machine learning

Photovoltaic systems

Power stability optimization

Real-time control

ABSTRACT

Photovoltaic (PV) systems often face real-time power stability challenges due to rapid fluctuations in solar irradiance and varying load conditions, which conventional control strategies struggle to manage effectively. Addressing this limitation, the present study proposes a novel machine learning-based control framework integrated with a hybrid inductor-capacitor (LC) network to enhance dynamic power regulation. The proposed system employs predictive algorithms to adjust LC parameters in real time, enabling adaptive voltage and current stabilization during transient conditions. Simulation results validate the model's effectiveness, showing a 58% reduction in power fluctuation (from 12% to 5%) and consistent improvement in voltage stability index (VSI), maintaining values above 0.95 compared to 0.88–0.93 in traditional systems. Moreover, the approach reduces computation time by 66% (150 ms versus 450 ms for PID-based systems), supporting faster and more efficient control actions. These outcomes demonstrate that the proposed intelligent control strategy significantly improves energy efficiency, voltage stability, and responsiveness in PV systems, offering a scalable solution for reliable grid integration of renewable energy sources.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

S. Pushpa

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Panimalar Engineering College

Chennai-600123, Tamil Nadu, India

Email: puvehava@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Electricity is fundamental to modern society, and the rising energy demand has intensified the need for reliable and sustainable power systems. Renewable energy sources, particularly photovoltaic (PV) systems, play a crucial role in reducing dependence on fossil fuels while ensuring environmental sustainability. Palensky and Dietrich [1] highlighted that demand-side management and intelligent energy systems are essential for optimizing load distribution and improving overall grid efficiency. Expanding on this, Kumar *et al.* [2] demonstrated that integrating demand response strategies with multi-microgrid systems enhances energy management and supports renewable energy penetration. In microgrid applications, voltage

regulation is vital for maintaining stability. Lakshmi *et al.* [3] showed that using a fractional order predictive-proportional integral controller for battery charging and discharging significantly improves voltage stability. Afshari *et al.* [4] proposed a robust cooperative control framework for isolated AC microgrids, addressing communication uncertainties to maintain reliable operation. Shwetha and Lakshmi [5] emphasized that DC–DC buck–boost converters are effective in managing renewable energy sources and biomedical applications through real-time IoT integration. Hybrid renewable energy systems further enhance efficiency and reliability. Iweh and Akupan [6] employed particle swarm optimization and differential evolution to optimize hybrid solar PV–hydro systems for off-grid applications, achieving improved energy management and reduced power losses. Kumar *et al.* [7] evaluated a 20 kW grid-connected PV installation, confirming that proper system design ensures sustainable energy delivery. Rakib *et al.* [8] demonstrated that energy-storage-based hybrid systems provide seamless renewable integration and strengthen grid stability. Akinwola and Alkuhayli [9] applied hybrid PSO–reinforcement learning for adaptive virtual inertia control, enhancing frequency stability in multi-microgrid PV systems. Similarly, Aldulaimi and Çevik [10] implemented AI enhanced MPPT using ANFIS-PSO optimization to improve grid-connected PV system performance.

Voltage stability remains a critical challenge in PV integration. Thota *et al.* [11] used IEEE 14 and 30 bus systems to analyze voltage stability under optimized control, while Boubii *et al.* [12] combined wind and solar power with advanced control strategies to maintain grid reliability [13]. Uswarman *et al.* [14] highlighted that hybrid energy storage in DC microgrids stabilizes bus voltage and enhances system resilience. Mamodiya *et al.* [15] applied AI-based hybrid solar energy systems with smart materials and adaptive PVs, demonstrating efficient power generation and dynamic load management. Al-Waeli *et al.* [16] and Kazem *et al.* [17] emphasized the role of neural networks and experimental evaluation in predicting PV/T system performance under variable conditions. Advanced control devices and algorithms further contribute to voltage management. Lakshmi [18] used a modified fuzzy logic controller for UPQC-integrated PV systems, while Sravani and Sobhan [19] assessed PV performance with custom power devices under different load conditions. Salama and Vokony [20] reviewed voltage stability indices, highlighting the need for effective metrics in grid-connected PV systems. Gebreabe *et al.* [21] provided a comprehensive review of photovoltaic, thermal, and hybrid systems, outlining sustainable energy solutions. Dhandapani *et al.* [22] demonstrated that solar PV integration enhances voltage stability in active distribution networks. Sreenivasan *et al.* [23] leveraged machine learning for renewable integration, and Abubakar *et al.* [24] optimized solar and wind generation using hybrid deep learning approaches. Finally, Zhang *et al.* [25] optimized passive damping for LCL-filtered PV-storage systems, ensuring improved dynamic response and reduced voltage oscillations.

2. METHOD

This study introduces a machine learning-based real-time power stability optimization model for PV systems, integrating hybrid inductor–capacitor (LC) patterns with intelligent circuit switching. The proposed design combines a predictive control layer with a hardware switching framework to maintain voltage stability and improve the power factor under dynamic environmental conditions. The hardware consists of K parallel LC branches, each comprising an inductor, capacitor, and MOSFET. At each control interval, only a subset of these branches is activated for charging or discharging based on the predicted impact on system stability. The selection process is driven by a trained machine learning (ML) model that evaluates real-time PV data and historical performance records to determine the optimal activation pattern.

2.1. Machine learning model

A multi-layer perceptron (MLP) neural network is employed due to its ability to handle nonlinear system behaviour, fast inference speed, and suitability for regression-based predictions.

Model Specifications:

- i) Inputs: PV input voltage (V_{in}), PV input current (i_{in}), solar irradiance, ambient temperature, individual capacitor voltages, inductor currents, and the previous activation pattern.
 - ii) Architecture: three hidden layers (64, 32, and 16 neurons) with ReLU activation functions.
 - iii) Outputs: for each candidate LC pattern, the model predicts:
 - Power fluctuation ΔP_{pred}
 - Voltage stability index (VSI_{pred})
 - Power loss ($P_{loss, pred}$)
 - iv) Loss function: mean squared error (MSE) between predicted and measured values.
 - v) Optimizer: Adam with a learning rate of 0.001.
- Training data: recorded PV operational data under diverse irradiance and load conditions, augmented to improve generalisation.

- vi) LC pattern generation:
At every control step, the system generates a set of feasible binary activation patterns for the K LC circuits:
- '1' indicates an active branch.
 - '0' indicates an idle branch.
- For example, with three LC branches, the possible patterns include:
[0,0,1], [1,1,0], [0,1,1], [1,1,1].....
- Patterns leading to excessive switching loss or component overloading are excluded from evaluation.
- vii) Pattern evaluation and selection:
Each generated pattern undergoes evaluation through the trained MLP model:
- Feature vector formation: combine current PV measurements and LC states into a single feature vector for each candidate pattern.
 - ML prediction: Estimate ΔP_{pred} , VSI_{pred} , and $P_{loss, pred}$.
 - Scoring: compute a weighted score:
Score (Pk) = $w_1 \cdot VSI_{pred} - w_2 \cdot \Delta P_{pred} - w_3 \cdot P_{loss, pred}$
where w_1 , w_2 , w_3 are tuning coefficients prioritising stability, low fluctuation, and minimal loss.
 - Selection: choose the pattern with the highest score for immediate activation.
 - Switching: activate selected branches for regulation; assign non-selected branches to charge mode.
- viii) Real-time control process:
Each control cycle (~150 ms) executes the following sequence:
- Acquire real-time PV and LC measurements.
 - Generate all valid LC activation patterns.
 - Predict stability and loss for each pattern using the MLP.
 - Select the highest-scoring pattern.
 - Trigger the corresponding MOSFETs for activation.
 - Store the results in the historical database for future model retraining
- ix) Key advantages:
- Rapid decision-making: Completes each optimisation cycle in ~150 ms, faster than fuzzy logic (300 ms) and PID (450 ms) controllers.
 - Proactive stability management: predicts and prevents instability before it occurs.
 - Loss reduction: avoids unnecessary activation of idle or saturated components.
 - High reliability: maintains $VSI > 0.95$ with power fluctuations limited to ~5%.

2.2. Hardware configuration

- i) PV source: 5 kW rooftop solar array, polycrystalline modules, STC efficiency: 18.5%, V_{oc} : 38.2 V/module.
- ii) Power conditioning unit: boost converter with MOSFET switching (IRFP460), switching frequency: 20 kHz.
- iii) Inductor–capacitor (LC) network:
 - 6 parallel circuits, each containing 1 inductor ($L = 4.7$ mH, copper core) and 1 capacitor ($C = 470$ μ F, electrolytic, 450 V rating).
 - Rated voltage: 400 V, continuous current: 15 A per branch.
- iv) Measurement devices: Hall-effect voltage and current sensors ($\pm 0.5\%$ accuracy).
- v) Control platform: TI TMS320F28379D DSP, 200 MHz, 16-bit ADC sampling at 50 kHz.
- vi) Data acquisition: irradiance sensor (± 5 W/m²), ambient temperature sensor (± 0.2 °C).

2.3. Software and algorithmic setup

- i) Programming environment: MATLAB/Simulink R2024a with embedded coder for DSP deployment
- ii) Machine learning model: multi-layer perceptron (MLP) regression model
 - Input features:
 - PV voltage (V_{in}), PV current (I_{in})
 - Irradiance (G), Temperature (T)
 - Capacitor voltages ($V_{C1} \dots V_{C6}$) and Inductor currents ($I_{L1} \dots I_{L6}$)
 - Binary LC activation pattern
 - Hidden layers: 3 fully connected layers (64–128–64 neurons) with ReLU activation
 - Output variables: predicted power fluctuation (ΔP_{pred}), Voltage Stability Index (VSI_{pred}), Predicted power loss (P_{loss_pred})
 - Training method: Adam optimizer, learning rate 0.001, batch size 64, 200 epochs

- Loss function: mean squared error (MSE)
- Training dataset: 30,000 real-time recorded operational cycles (70% training, 15% validation, 15% testing)
- iii) Optimization engine: genetic algorithm (GA) for LC pattern selection
 - Population size: 20 patterns per cycle
 - Selection: tournament selection (size = 3)
 - Crossover: single-point, rate = 0.8
 - Mutation: bit-flip, rate = 0.05
 - Fitness function: $\text{Score} = w_1 \times \text{VSI}_{\text{pred}} - w_2 \times \Delta P_{\text{pred}} - w_3 \times P_{\text{loss_pred}}$, where $w_1 = 0.5$, $w_2 = 0.3$, $w_3 = 0.2$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study “MLP with GA-based pattern selection real-time power stability optimisation for photovoltaic systems using hybrid inductor-capacitor patterns” aims to increase 5 kW rooftop PV array systems' efficiency and stability. The experimental setup consisted of six parallel LC branches (4.7 mH inductors, 470 μF capacitors, 450 V rating) connected via MOSFET switches controlled by the DSP-based system. The system can anticipate and optimize electricity output in real time, adjusting to changing environmental conditions, by utilizing machine learning algorithms. By reducing fluctuations, the incorporation of hybrid inductor-capacitor circuits improves power stability even more. The outcomes show notable gains in energy efficiency, decreased system instability, and improved power quality, guaranteeing that PV systems maximise energy yield while operating at their best under dynamic situations.

3.1. Fluctuation analysis of power

Figure 1 demonstrates ML-based hybrid LC system reduces power fluctuations to 5%, compared to 12% in conventional systems a 58% improvement. This is achieved through adaptive control of LC patterns, enabling real-time disturbance correction and stable power output. Circuit activation decisions are optimized using weighted scores (0.5:0.3:0.2 for stability, fluctuation minimization, and loss reduction). The system maintains a voltage stability index (VSI) above 0.95, outperforming traditional systems that vary between 0.88 and 0.93. Hybrid LC patterns are optimized in real time using a Genetic Algorithm for maximum VSI and minimal fluctuation. This ensures reliable grid operation, improved power quality, and reduced equipment stress.

As shown in Figure 2, the ML-driven system maintains a consistently high voltage stability index (VSI) above 0.95 throughout a 10-hour period, while conventional systems show greater variation between 0.88 and 0.93. This indicates enhanced voltage regulation achieved through dynamic impedance management and topology adjustments, which helps prevent voltage dips and spikes, protecting equipment and ensuring steady grid operation. Figure 3 highlights the system's capability to quickly respond to changes in solar radiation, stabilizing power output faster than traditional approaches, thereby maximizing energy harvesting under varying environmental conditions.

Figure 1. Analysis of power stability over time

Figure 2. Enhanced power generation in response to solar radiation

Figure 3. Faster stabilization

The power loss analysis in Figure 4 confirms that the proposed method significantly lowers energy losses across different operational scenarios compared to standard methods, improving overall system efficiency. Figure 5 illustrates consistent decline in training and validation loss, reflecting the model's effective learning and generalization capabilities, crucial for reliable real-time control. In Figure 6, the close alignment between predicted and actual stability values validates the accuracy of the ML model in forecasting system behavior, supporting precise power management. The ML-based approach requires approximately 150 ms per computation cycle, substantially faster than PID (450 ms) and fuzzy logic (300 ms) controllers. This rapid processing enables swift system responses to changing conditions, essential for large-scale photovoltaic installations facing variable weather.

Our findings build upon previous research, such as demonstration of ML with hybrid LC networks for stabilizing power output, and Zhang *et al.*'s work [25] on voltage regulation improvements. However, this study introduces real-time pattern-based circuit selection, offering superior reduction in power fluctuations and enhanced voltage stability beyond earlier models. The dynamic control strategy here addresses limitations like power loss and circuit saturation that prior approaches did not fully resolve.

Figure 4. Power loss reduction across scenarios

Figure 5. Training and validation loss

Figure 6. ML model accuracy: predicted vs. actual stability

4. CONCLUSION

This study introduces a machine learning-based model integrating real-time control with hybrid LC selection to enhance power stability in photovoltaic systems. It achieves a 58% reduction in power fluctuations and maintains a voltage stability index above 0.95. The proposed method improves computation speed by 66% compared to conventional PID controllers. This establishes it as a scalable solution for intelligent PV energy management. Future work will focus on integrating deep reinforcement learning and optimizing the model for decentralized microgrids. Extending it to hybrid PV-battery systems can further enhance adaptability and resilience.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Authors state no funding involved.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Jayashree Kathirvel	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓
S. Pushpa	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				✓
P. Kavitha	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓			✓
Sathya Sureshkumar		✓				✓			✓					
Kannan Andi					✓		✓			✓		✓		✓
Prabakaran Pramasivam	✓					✓				✓				

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data availability is not applicable to this paper as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Palensky and D. Dietrich, "Demand side management: demand response, intelligent energy systems, and smart loads," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 381–388, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TII.2011.2158841.
- [2] S. S. Kumar, V. Pramila, S. Rudhra, S. Vinod, and D. Lakshmi, "Enhancing demand response and energy management in multi-microgrid systems with renewable energy sources," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 253, p. 123490, Nov. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2025.123490.
- [3] D. Lakshmi, J. V. Anand, S. Baskaran, M. D. Babu, and S. S. Kumar, "Enhanced voltage regulation for microgrids with battery charger/discharger using fractional order predictive-proportional integral controller," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 123, p. 116703, Jul. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2025.116703.
- [4] A. Afshari, M. Karrari, H. R. Baghaee, G. B. Gharehpetian, and J. M. Guerrero, "Robust cooperative control of isolated AC microgrids subject to unreliable communications: a low-gain feedback approach," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 55–66, 2022, doi: 10.1109/JSYST.2021.3056481.
- [5] M. Shwetha and S. Lakshmi, "DC-DC buck boost converter for renewable and biomedical application based real-time," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 328–336, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.35940/ijrte.D6841.118419.
- [6] C. D. Iweh and E. R. Akupan, "Control and optimization of a hybrid solar PV – hydro power system for off-grid applications using particle swarm optimization (PSO) and differential evolution (DE)," *Energy Reports*, vol. 10, pp. 4253–4270, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2023.10.080.
- [7] K. A. Kumar, K. Sundareswaran, and P. R. Venkateswaran, "Performance study on a grid connected 20 kW p solar photovoltaic installation in an industry in Tiruchirappalli (India)," *Energy for Sustainable Development*, vol. 23, pp. 294–304, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.esd.2014.10.002.
- [8] M. W. Rakib, A. H. Munna, T. Farooq, A. Boker, and M. He, "Enhancing grid stability and sustainability: energy-storage-based hybrid systems for seamless renewable integration," *European Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1–8, May 2024, doi: 10.24018/ejece.2024.8.3.618.

- [9] A. B. Akinwola and A. Alkuhayli, "Hybrid PSO–reinforcement learning-based adaptive virtual inertia control for frequency stability in multi-microgrid PV systems," *Electronics*, vol. 14, no. 17, p. 3349, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.3390/electronics14173349.
- [10] M. Y. M. Aldulaimi and M. Çevik, "AI-Enhanced MPPT control for grid-connected photovoltaic systems using ANFIS-PSO optimization," *Electronics*, vol. 14, no. 13, p. 2649, Jun. 2025, doi: 10.3390/electronics14132649.
- [11] P. K. Thota, G. Somaskandan, and M. Mani, "The voltage stability analysis for grid-connected PV system using optimized control tested by IEEE 14 & 30 bus system," *International Journal of Experimental Research and Review*, vol. 30, pp. 109–118, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.52756/ijerr.2023.v30.012.
- [12] C. Boubii *et al.*, "Synergizing wind and solar power: an advanced control system for grid stability," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 2, p. 815, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.3390/su16020815.
- [13] S. Selvi, J. A. Kumar, M. Joly, and B. Rampriya, "Levy based smooth synchronization of microgrid integrated with multiple renewable sources," *Electrical Engineering*, vol. 106, no. 6, pp. 8003–8016, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00202-024-02494-6.
- [14] R. Usvarman, K. Munawar, M. A. M. Ramli, and I. M. Mehedi, "Bus voltage stabilization of a sustainable photovoltaic-fed DC microgrid with hybrid energy storage systems," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 6, p. 2307, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.3390/su16062307.
- [15] U. Mamodiya, I. Kishor, R. Garine, P. Ganguly, and N. Naik, "Artificial intelligence based hybrid solar energy systems with smart materials and adaptive photovoltaics for sustainable power generation," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 17370, May 2025, doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-01788-4.
- [16] A. H. A. Al-Waeli, H. A. Kazem, J. H. Yousif, M. T. Chaichan, and K. Sopian, "Mathematical and neural network models for predicting the electrical performance of a PV/T system," *International Journal of Energy Research*, p. er.4807, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1002/er.4807.
- [17] H. A. Kazem *et al.*, "Performance evaluation of solar photovoltaic/thermal system performance: An experimental and artificial neural network approach," *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, vol. 61, p. 104860, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.csite.2024.104860.
- [18] S. Lakshmi, "Solar PV integrated UPQC modelling and control using modified fuzzy logic controller," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 10, no. 09, 2021, doi: 10.17577/IJERTV10IS090013.
- [19] M. Sravani and P. V. S. Sobhan, "Performance evaluation of solar PV integrated with custom power device under various load conditions," *e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, vol. 10, p. 100843, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.prime.2024.100843.
- [20] H. S. Salama and I. Vokony, "Voltage stability indices—a comparison and a review," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 98, p. 107743, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.107743.
- [21] S. T. Gebreabe, D. Bogale, A. Hailu, and A. Worku, "Advances in solar energy technologies: a comprehensive review of photovoltaic, thermal, and hybrid systems for sustainable energy solutions," *Next Research*, vol. 3, p. 101176, Jan. 2026, doi: 10.1016/j.nexres.2025.101176.
- [22] L. Dhandapani, P. Sreenivasan, S. Murugan, H. Maria, and S. Banerjee, "Enhancing voltage stability in active distribution networks through solar PV integration," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 16, no. 2, p. 1137, Jun. 2025, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v16.i2.pp1137-1146.
- [23] P. Sreenivasan, K. Ganesan, I. Fawad, S. Sureshkumar, and K. Dhandapani, "Leveraging machine learning for sustainable integration of renewable energy generation," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 36, no. 3, p. 1347, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v36.i3.pp1347-1355.
- [24] M. Abubakar, Y. Che, A. Zafar, M. A. Al-Khasawneh, and M. S. Bhutta, "Optimization of solar and wind power plants production through a parallel fusion approach with modified hybrid machine and deep learning models," *Intelligent Data Analysis*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 808–830, 2025, doi: 10.1177/1088467X241312592.
- [25] Y. Zhang, C. Song, T. Wang, and K. Wang, "Optimization of passive damping for LCL-filtered AC grid-connected PV-storage integrated systems," *Electronics*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 801, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.3390/electronics14040801.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Jayashree Kathirvel completed her bachelor degree (2002) in Sona College of Technology, Salem, and completed her master degree (2010) in Indian Institute of Technology, Madras. She is currently working as assistant professor (senior grade), in Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department at Rajalakshmi Engineering College, Chennai. She is currently pursuing her Ph.D. at Anna University, Chennai. Her current research area includes hybrid renewable energy systems, investigation on converter topologies for electric vehicles, FACTS devices, and power system stability and control. She can be contacted at email: jayasree.k@rajalakshmi.edu.in.

S. Pushpa is a research scholar in Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department at the Academy of Maritime Education (AMET) University, Tamil Nadu, India. She has 18 years of teaching experience. She received her B.E. degree in electrical and electronics engineering from Madras University in the year 2003, M.E. degree in power system engineering in Anna University, Tamil Nadu, India, in the year 2009, respectively. She is currently an assistant professor at Panimalar Engineering College, Tamil Nadu, India. Her research interests include the field of power systems, renewable energy, electrical machines, control systems, and microgrids. She is a life member in professional bodies like IAENG. She got an organiser award in Green Energy SDG. She can be contacted at email: puvehava@gmail.com.

Dr. P. Kavitha working as an associate professor in the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering R.M.K Engineering College, has about 27 years of teaching experience. She received her B.E. degree in electrical and electronics engineering with first class and M.E. degree in control and instrumentation with distinction from Anna University, Chennai. She has published 17 research papers in refereed international journals and various international conferences. She has received the best paper award for her research paper at IET international conference. Her areas of research include power controllers, machine design, and renewable energy systems. She is a member of ISOI and ISTE. She can be contacted at email: pkt.eee@rmkec.ac.in.

Mrs. Sathya Sureshkumar received the B.E. degree in electronics and communication engineering from Madras University, Chennai, in 2004, M.E. degree in power electronics and drives from Anna University, CEG, Chennai, in 2013, and is currently pursuing Ph.D. at Anna University, Chennai. She has been with S.A. Engineering College, where she is currently an assistant professor with the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering. She has a total experience of 15 years in the field of teaching and has published papers in various international journals and conferences. Her areas of research are in-situ process monitoring and defect detection of additive manufacturing components using image processing and machine learning. She can be contacted at email: sathyas@sacc.ac.in.

Kannan Andi obtained his B.E. in electrical and electronics engineering from Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, Sivakasi, M.Tech. in applied electronics, and Ph.D. in power quality from Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institute, Chennai. He has over two decades of teaching and research experience in reputed institutions. He has authored three books and published several research papers in national and international journals. He received the MGR Research Award for his research contributions in 2015. Currently, he is a Professor in the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering at Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institute, Chennai. He can be contacted at email: drkannan1976@gmail.com.

Prabakaran Pramasivam obtained B.E. degree in electrical and electronics engineering from Dr. Navalar Nudunchezhiyan College of Engineering, Tholudar, Cuddalore District M.Tech. degree in power electronics drive from Dr MGR University, Maduravayal, Chennai and Ph.D. in the area of performance analysis and comparison of various control algorithm for photovoltaic inverter from Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research University - Chennai. More than 10 years experience industry and IT field HT/LT project and maintenance work. Currently, he is working as an assistant professor in Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department, Chennai Institute of Technology in Chennai. He can be contacted at email: prabakaranp.eee@citchennai.net.